

Supporting researchers in data driven Life Sciences & Health across the Netherlands

We connect communities, infrastructures and expertise to strengthen digital research capabilities in Life Sciences & Health. **We connect people to useful guidance and resources.**

Get help sharing and managing data

The research data management toolkit for life sciences, including best practices and guidelines. <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org>

Practical guidance to make your life sciences and health data FAIR, from planning to implementation. <https://fairmetroline.org>

A curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, interrelated to databases and data policies. <https://fairsharing.org>

Find tools and training

Essential information about software tools, databases and services for bioinformatics and life sciences. <https://bio.tools>

Open, web-based platform for data-intensive computational research. <https://usegalaxy.eu>

A registry for describing, sharing and publishing scientific computational workflows. <https://workflowhub.eu>

One-stop shop for training materials, events and interactive tutorials. <https://tess.elixir-europe.org>

Connect to the communities

Interoperability, digital infrastructure, metadata, vocabularies, standards and tools. <https://tdcc.nl/network/dutch-interoperability-network>

For bioinformatics and systems biology research in the Netherlands. <https://www.dtls.nl/biosb>

Building a digital environment to make life science research data accessible and exchangeable. <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/nodes/netherlands>

Community hub for data stewardship, exchanging knowledge and experience. <https://tdcc.nl/network/dsig>

Get to know our projects

Our projects further support the TDCC network and contribute to the digitalisation of science more broadly. Current funded project topics include:

- Fellowship programme
- Practical FAIR metadata
- FAIR educational alignment
- FAIR awareness and AI savviness for data scientists
- FAIRifying metabolomics data
- Core dataset for cohort studies
- FAIR tool framework
- Interoperability in life sciences and health

<https://tdcc.nl/projects/tdcc-lsh-project-initiatives>

If you are interested in one of these topics, would like to join an initiative or want to launch a new initiative, please contact us via our website.

Find more information on our website

<https://tdcc.nl/lsh>

Check out the digital version of the flyer

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